

AWARENESS AND IMPLEMENTATION OF DISASTER PREPAREDNESS OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL IN BUGUIAS DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on disaster preparedness of the 44 public elementary schools in Buguias District. The study used the descriptive method using the survey questionnaire as a data gathering tool to the 1,263 respondents including the school heads, teachers, SDDRM Coordinator and Grade six learners of elementary schools in Buguias District. The study used the mean to describe the level of awareness and extent of implementation of stakeholders while one way ANOVA was used to show the significant difference on the level of awareness and extent of implementation when respondents are grouped according to their profiles. The findings shows that stake holders were very much aware on disaster preparedness program of the school. In finding the significant difference on the level of awareness when respondents are grouped according to their profile it shows no significant difference. In the extent of implementation stakeholders' participation on the programs of the school is much implemented. And in finding the significant difference on the extent of implementation of disaster preparedness program when respondents are grouped according to their profile shows no significant difference. Overall, the result shows very high level of awareness and moderately low implementation where stake holders are expected to be more participative in disaster preparedness programs of the school.

Keywords: *Disaster Preparedness, Stakeholders, Awareness, Implementation*

INTRODUCTION

Catastrophes, such as earthquakes, floods, and typhoons, pose significant risks worldwide, impacting lives, properties, and economies. Recent years have seen an increase in the frequency and severity of these natural disasters, exacerbated by climate

change. In 2022, storm-related damages were projected to exceed \$130 billion globally. The Philippines, located in the Pacific Ring of Fire, is particularly vulnerable to these events. For instance, Typhoon Ompong in 2018 and the 7.0-magnitude earthquake in 2022 caused extensive damage to infrastructure, including schools, highlighting the need for effective disaster preparedness.

In response to these challenges, various international and national frameworks have been established. The Sendai Framework (2015-2030) emphasizes understanding disaster risk, investing in disaster risk reduction, and improving preparedness for effective response. The Philippine Disaster Risk Management Act of 2010 (RA 10121) aims to transform disaster response from a reactive to a proactive approach, emphasizing community-based disaster risk management. The Department of Education (DepEd) has mandated the integration of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) into the educational system to ensure the safety and preparedness of school communities.

Effective disaster preparedness involves all stakeholders, including school heads, teachers, parents, and students. Prior studies highlight the importance of community engagement and the role of education in enhancing disaster resilience. School evacuation drills and disaster preparedness training are critical in equipping students and staff with the necessary skills to respond to emergencies. Despite these efforts, gaps remain in the actual implementation of disaster preparedness measures in schools.

This study aims to assess the level of awareness and implementation of disaster preparedness among stakeholders in public elementary schools in Buguias. It seeks to determine differences in awareness and implementation based on stakeholder profiles and develop a comprehensive disaster preparedness plan based on the findings. The study's outcomes will inform the development of targeted training programs and interventions to improve disaster preparedness in schools, ensuring the safety and resilience of students and staff in the face of natural disasters.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effect of 5E instructional model to the academic performance in Mathematics of grade 7 students.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of awareness of the stakeholders of public elementary schools in Buguias on disaster preparedness as perceived by:
 - a) school heads
 - b) teachers
 - c) SDRRM Coordinators
 - d) PTA Presidents
 - e) pupils
2. Is there a difference in the level of awareness of the stakeholders when grouped according to their profile?
3. What is the extent of the level of implementation of the stakeholders of the public elementary schools on disaster preparedness as perceived by:

- a) school heads
 - b) teachers
 - c) SDRRM Coordinators
 - d) PTA Presidents
 - e) pupils
4. Is there a difference in the extent of implementation of the stakeholders when grouped according to their profile?
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METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research design to assess the level of awareness and implementation of disaster preparedness among stakeholders in public elementary schools in Buguias District for the school year 2023-2024. The descriptive method was chosen for its efficacy in gathering detailed and accurate information about the current state of disaster preparedness. The study aimed to judge the level of awareness and implementation without manipulating any variables, thus ensuring a realistic portrayal of the existing situation. A standardized survey method using questionnaires served as the primary instrument for data collection, providing a structured approach to capture the perspectives of various stakeholders comprehensively.

The study was conducted in Buguias, Benguet, targeting specific groups within the public elementary schools: teachers, PTA Presidents, SDRRM Coordinators, school heads, and Grade 6 pupils. These groups were selected due to their critical roles in disaster preparedness and response within the school community. Grade 6 pupils were chosen specifically because of their advanced cognitive abilities compared to younger students, enabling them to understand survey questions better and provide more accurate responses. Their prolonged exposure to the school environment also made them valuable sources of insight regarding the school's disaster preparedness measures. The total enumeration method was used to ensure that the entire population of the identified groups was included in the study, maximizing the comprehensiveness and reliability of the findings.

The data collection process began with obtaining permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Benguet. Upon approval, the researcher, with the assistance of colleagues, distributed the questionnaires to the respondents. Clear communication regarding the purpose and importance of the study was provided to ensure informed participation. The respondents were given adequate time to complete the questionnaires, after which the data was collected for analysis. This systematic approach ensured that the data collection process was thorough and that respondents understood their role and the significance of their input in enhancing the school's disaster preparedness.

The gathered data was meticulously tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using descriptive statistics, with a particular focus on the weighted mean to evaluate the level of awareness of disaster preparedness. A four-point Likert scale was employed to quantify responses, providing clear statistical limits and descriptive equivalents. To

determine if there were significant differences in awareness and implementation levels based on the respondents' roles within the school, a one-way ANOVA was conducted. This statistical method was chosen for its ability to compare means across multiple groups effectively. The results were further validated using the Microsoft Analysis Tool Pack, ensuring the robustness and accuracy of the findings. This rigorous treatment of data ensured that the conclusions drawn were well-supported and reliable, forming a solid foundation for any subsequent recommendations or action plans.

RESULTS

Table 1. Level of Academic Performance of the Grade 7 Learners Based on their Pre-test Scores

Respondents	Scores	Level of Performance
pondents Scores Level of Performance	pondents Scores Level of Performance	pondents Scores Level of Performance
1	18	S
2	26	VS
3	9	FS
4	18	S
5	14	FS
6	8	DNME
7	21	S
8	24	S
9	10	FS
10	19	S
11	12	FS
12	28	VS
13	28	VS
14	16	FS
15	23	S
16	15	FS
17	21	S
18	24	S
19	10	FS
20	9	FS
21	7	DNME
22	7	DNME
23	9	FS
24	22	S
25	21	S
26	18	S
Total	437	
Mean	16.81	FS

Table 2. Level of Academic Performance of the Grade 7 Learners Based on their Posttest Scores

Respondents	Scores	Level of Performance
1	27	VS
2	24	S
3	22	S
4	25	VS
5	27	VS
6	30	VS
7	29	VS
8	22	S
9	34	O
10	14	FS
11	27	VS
12	16	FS
13	30	VS
14	20	S
15	24	S
16	35	O
17	22	S
18	29	VS
19	21	S
20	39	O
21	19	S
22	24	S
23	39	O
24	23	S
25	25	VS
26	19	S
Total	666	
Mean	25.62	VS

Table 3. Difference in the Scores of the Learners from the Pretest to the Posttest

Respondents	Pre-test	Post-test	D	D ²
1	18	27	9	81
2	26	24	-2	4
3	9	22	13	169
4	18	25	7	49
5	14	27	13	169
6	8	30	22	484
7	21	29	8	64
8	24	22	-2	4
9	10	34	24	576
10	19	14	-5	25
11	12	27	15	225
12	28	16	-12	144
13	28	30	2	4
14	16	20	4	16
15	23	24	1	1

16	15	35	20	400
17	21	22	1	1
18	24	29	5	25
19	10	21	11	121
20	9	39	30	900
21	7	19	12	144
22	7	24	17	289
23	9	39	30	900
24	22	23	1	1
25	21	25	4	16
26	18	19	1	1
Total	437	666	229	4813
Mean	16.81 FS	25.62 VS	8.81	

DISCUSSION

Level of Awareness on Disaster Preparedness of Public Elementary Schools

Table 1 presents the answers of respondents on the level of awareness of stakeholders of public elementary schools in disaster preparedness regarding safe learning environment. The result shows that stakeholders are fully aware of disaster preparedness programs regarding safe learning environment at school as manifested in the average mean of 3.66 interpreted as very much aware. It is associated with the stakeholder's awareness a copy of community hazard map to be posted at school is

provided by the Department of Science and Technology can be secured at the respective local government having the highest mean of 3.76.

Table 1: Level of awareness of stakeholders on disaster preparedness regarding safe learning environment

SAFE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT	M	DE
1. Disaster preparedness program is implemented in every school such as capacity building for stakeholders, integration of DRRM in the curriculum, School Based DRRM Committee and Brigada Eskwila.	3.66	VMA
2. A copy of community hazard map to be posted at school is provided by the Department of Science and Technology can be secured at the respective local government.	3.76	VMA
3. Conduct of school building inspection through partnership with local engineers from municipal government, Department of Public Work and Highways (DPWH), and the Bureau of Fire Protection.	3.56	VMA
4. Conduct of fire safety inspection through partnership with local engineers from municipal government, Department of Public Work and Highways (DPWH), and the Bureau of Fire Protection.	3.68	VMA
5. School has a clearly defined signages in every part of the school, as needed.	3.65	VMA
6. Stakeholders participates in construction of the school to provide safe and conducive place for learning.	3.63	VMA
Average Mean	3.66	VMA

LEGEND: 3.26-4.00 *Very Much Aware (VMA)*
 2.51-3.25 *Much Aware (MA)*
 1.76-2.50 *Aware (A)*
 1.00-1.75 *Not Aware (NA)*

The area obtaining the lowest mean is 3.56 interpreted as very much aware the Conduct of school building inspection through partnership with local engineers from municipal government, Department of Public Work and Highways (DPWH), and the Bureau of Fire Protection. The result tells us that stakeholders are knowledgeable of school's program regarding safe learning environment. The very much aware result of stakeholders' awareness on disaster preparedness regarding safe learning environment contradicts with the study of Tuladhar et al. (2015) where teachers are not well informed and aware of the programs about disaster preparedness regarding school safe environment. This result differs from the outcome of the research as such that only teachers were measured during the conduct of the study. Furthermore, the methodology that they have used was histogram analysis and t-test to get the result while in this study

it uses the mean to determine the stakeholder's awareness. The graphical representation shows thorough representation of the data gathered as seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Level of awareness of stakeholders on disaster preparedness regarding school disaster management.

SCHOOL DISASTER MANAGEMENT	M	DE
1. There is an SDRRM Team organized at school that will facilitate and oversee the implementation of DRRM Programs specifically on disaster preparedness.	3.27	VMA
2. The SDRRM Team conducts yearly DRRM Activities such as fire and earthquake drills as mandated by the Department of Education.	3.69	VMA
3. The school has a bulletin board where the profile of the school including DRRM information are posted.	3.74	VMA
4. An updated evacuation plan is provided and posted at the school to provide guidance in setting the schools evacuation procedure.	3.62	VMA
5. Yearly training needs analysis is conducted to be able to design appropriate training program for the SDRRM Team.	3.70	VMA
Average Mean	3.60	VMA

LEGEND: 3.26-4.00 *Very Much Aware (VMA)*
 2.51-3.25 *Much Aware (MA)*
 1.76-2.50 *Aware (A)*
 1.00-1.75 *Not Aware (NA)*

Table 2 shows that stakeholders are very much aware of disaster preparedness with regards to school disaster management evident with the average mean of 3.60 interpreted as very much aware. The area obtaining the highest mean is the school having a bulletin board where the profile of the school including the DRRM information is posted obtaining the highest mean of 3.74. Obtaining lowest mean is 3.27 interpreted as very much aware where stakeholders' awareness that there is an SDRRM Team organized at school that will facilitate and oversee the implementation of DRRM Programs specifically

on disaster preparedness. Overall, the result shows that stakeholders are very much aware of the programs of school regarding school disaster management.

The result corroborates to the study of Marskole et al. (2018) where after their intervention on disaster management program was done 110 or 87.2% of their respondents are highly knowledgeable about school disaster management.

Table 3: Level of awareness of stakeholders on disaster preparedness regarding risk reduction and resilience education.

RISK REDUCTION AND RESELIENCE EDUCATION	M	DE
1. Disaster Risk Reduction and Management activities are included in co-curricular activities such as family day, IP Month and Linggo ng Wika.	3.62	VMA
2. The school through DepEd Order No. 5 s. 2014, participates in Gulayan sa Paaralan, ecological waste management and tree growing and caring.	3.62	VMA
3. Disaster Risk Reduction posters are seen at the school vicinity.	3.62	VMA
4. There are active community organizations that promote and support school's endeavors on DRRM like local non- government organizations, religious institutions, community education and others.	3.57	VMA
5. Stakeholders are involved in planning of the activities for the school by the SDRRM Team.	3.59	VMA
Average Mean	3.60	MA

LEGEND: 3.26-4.00 Very Much Aware (VMA)
 2.51-3.25 Much Aware (MA)
 1.76-2.50 Aware (A)
 1.00-1.75 Not Aware (NA)

Table 3 presents the awareness of stakeholders on disaster preparedness regarding risk reduction and resilience education where the result shows that stakeholders are very much aware as shown in the average mean of 3.60 interpreted as very much aware. The result is associated with the stakeholder's awareness on disaster risk reduction and management activities are included in co-curricular activities such as family day, IP Month and Linggo ng Wika, the school through DepEd Order No. 5 s. 2014, participates in Gulayan sa Paaralan, ecological waste management and tree growing and caring and Disaster Risk Reduction posters are seen at the school vicinity with a mean of 3.62. Obtaining the lowest mean is there are active community organizations that promote and support school's endeavors on DRRM like local non- government organizations, religious institutions, community education and others with a mean of 3.57.

The result of the study does not corroborate to the study of Shah et al. (2019) wherein schools are not fully aware of the disaster preparedness program regarding risk

reduction and education as to the response of their respondents. The result differs because the study was conducted in other country with 40 key informants from 19 institution as their respondents.

Table 4: Level of awareness of stakeholders on disaster preparedness regarding communication and information sources.

COMMUNICATION AND INFORMATION SOURCES	M	DE
1. There are available communication channel that stakeholders can access/ receive information regarding Disaster Risk Reduction and Management.	3.59	VMA
2. There are available information sources that stakeholders can access/ receive information regarding Disaster Risk Reduction and Management.	3.63	VMA
3. Posters of updated emergency numbers are posted in important places in the school like the classroom and offices.	3.58	VMA
4. Stakeholders are active in participating in the Information Education Campaign of the SDDRM Team.	3.67	VMA
5. The school conducts meetings with stakeholders regarding disaster preparedness activities of school.	3.52	VMA
6. The school organizes the SPG (Supreme Student Government) that helps in the information dissemination and communication of disaster preparedness program of the school.	3.75	VMA
Average Mean	3.62	VMA

LEGEND: 3.26-4.00 *Very Much Aware (VMA)*
 2.51-3.25 *Much Aware (MA)*
 1.76-2.50 *Aware (A)*
 1.00-1.75 *Not Aware (NA)*

Table 4 presents the stakeholders awareness on disaster preparedness program with regards to communication and information sources where the stakeholders are very much aware evident with the average mean of 3.62 interpreted as very much aware. The result is associated with the stakeholders organizing the SPG (Supreme Student Government) that helps in the information dissemination and communication of disaster preparedness program of the school obtaining the highest mean of 3.75. Obtaining the lowest mean is the school conducts meetings with stakeholders regarding disaster preparedness activities of school with a mean of 3.52 still interpreted as very much aware.

The result implies that stakeholders are knowledgeable in communication and information sources regarding disaster preparedness.

Table 5 Level of awareness of stakeholders on disaster preparedness

<u>LEVEL OF DISASTER AWARENESS OF STAKEHOLDERS</u>	<u>M</u>	<u>DE</u>
<u>Safe Learning Environment</u>	<u>3.66</u>	<u>VMA</u>
<u>School Disaster Management</u>	<u>3.60</u>	<u>VMA</u>
<u>Risk Reduction and Resilience Education</u>	<u>3.60</u>	<u>VMA</u>
<u>Communication and Information Sources</u>	<u>3.62</u>	<u>VMA</u>
<u>General Average Mean</u>	<u>3.62</u>	<u>VMA</u>

The level of awareness of stakeholders on the school disaster preparedness programs is very much aware based on the total average mean of 3.62 interpreted by the descriptive equivalent as very much aware as shown in table 6. Safe learning environment obtained the highest mean of 3.66 while school disaster management and risk reduction in education obtained the lowest mean of 3.60.

The result corroborates with the study Ventura et al. (2020) wherein their respondent's awareness on disaster preparedness program implemented in their school is very high meaning they are knowledgeable. It also agrees with the study of Marpa and Juele (2016) where their respondents were learners that shows high response in their awareness regarding disaster preparedness program.

Difference in the Level of Awareness of Public Elementary Schools stakeholders when grouped according to school profile

As shown in table 6, SDRRM Coordinators obtained the highest perception in terms of their awareness on disaster preparedness at school as shown in the mean of 3.70, followed by the teachers and school heads with the mean of 3.69. The Grade six pupils came in third with an average mean of 3.60. The lowest in mean is 3.50 which is obtained by the PTA Presidents. Nevertheless, the mean of the five group, though interpreted as very much aware, it reveals slight numerical differences. The difference lies in the areas of safe learning environment and school disaster management in which

SDRRM Coordinators and teachers have the highest rating of 3.81 as compared with the PTA presidents, Grade six learners and school heads.

Table 6 Difference on the Level of Awareness on disaster preparedness of public elementary schools when grouped according to the profile of the respondents.

Indicator	PTA President	Teachers	Grade Six Pupils	SDRRM Coordinators	School Heads
A. Safe Learning Environment	3.70	3.81	3.59	3.64	3.70
B. School Disaster Management	3.58	3.49	3.64	3.81	3.59
C. Risk Reduction and Resilience Education	3.53	3.71	3.55	3.78	3.79
D. Communication and Information Sources	3.54	3.66	3.61	3.56	3.67
Average	3.59	3.69	3.60	3.70	3.69

p-value= 0.37

$\alpha= 0.05$

not significant

Statistical analysis shows that the p-value of 0.37 is higher than the alpha value of 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the awareness of public elementary schools in disaster preparedness when school profile is considered.

The finding implies that regardless of the school profiles of respondents, stakeholders have similar perceptions, indicating that their school profile is not a factor in their awareness on disaster preparedness programs.

The findings of this study corroborate with the study of Cubillas et al. (2022) wherein their discoveries in their examination showed that the members displayed great mindfulness in the space of hazard decrease and flexibility schooling, safe learning conditions, debacle risk the executives, and empowering conditions, as well as exceptionally fulfilling mindfulness in these areas.

Extent of Implementation of Disaster Preparedness of Public Elementary Schools in Buguias

Not only should stakeholders be aware of disaster preparedness but should involve themselves in the implementation of school disaster management programs. With this it could reduce the risks that the school may suffer from various disasters. The

SDRRM Manual Book 1 and 2 by the Department of education listed the activities that schools should implement in relation to disaster preparedness as seen in table 4.

Table 8 Extent of implementation of disaster preparedness regarding safe learning environment

SAFE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT	M	DE
1. Disaster preparedness program is implemented in every school such as capacity building for stakeholders, integration of DRRM in the curriculum, School Based DRRM Committee and Brigada Eskwila.	3.39	VMI
2. A copy of community hazard map to be posted at school is provided by the Depart of Science and Technology can be secured at the respective local government.	2.03	I
3. Conduct of school building inspection through partnership with local engineers from municipal government, Department of Public Work and Highways (DPWH), and the Bureau of Fire Protection.	2.25	I
4. Conduct of fire safety inspection through partnership with local engineers from municipal government, Department of Public Work and Highways (DPWH), and the Bureau of Fire Protection.	2.76	MI
5. School has a clearly defined signages in every part of the school, as needed.	2.85	MI
6. Stakeholders participates in construction of the school to provide safe and conducive place for learning.	3.03	MI
Average Mean	2.72	MI

LEGEND: 3.26-4.00 *Very Much Implemented (VMI)*
 2.51-3.25 *Much Implemented (MI)*
 1.76-2.50 *Implemented (I)*
 1.00-1.75 *Not Implemented (NI)*

Table 8 shows the stakeholders extent of implementation on disaster preparedness with regards to safe learning environment. The result shows that stakeholders moderately implemented the programs associated with it evident in the average mean of 2.72 interpreted as moderately implemented. The result is associated with the stakeholder’s disaster preparedness program is implemented in every school such as capacity building for stakeholders, integration of DRRM in the curriculum, School Based DRRM Committee and Brigada Eskwila obtaining a mean of 3.39 with descriptive equivalent of very much implemented. Obtaining the least mean of 2.03 interpreted as implemented is a copy of community hazard map to be posted at school is provided by the Department of Science and Technology can be secured at the respective local

government. This implies that stakeholder's implementation on the programs regarding safe learning environment is moderately low.

The result corroborates to the study of Rofiah et al. (2021) where respondents have a low implementation of disaster preparedness programs specially that respondents specially teachers who do not have the necessary materials for the implementation of the program.

Table 9 Extent of implementation of disaster preparedness regarding school disaster management

SCHOOL DISASTER MANAGEMENT	M	DE
1. There is an SDRRM Team organized at school that will facilitate and oversee the implementation of DRRM Programs specifically on disaster preparedness.	3.42	VMI
2. The SDRRM Team conducts yearly DRRM Activities such as fire and earthquake drills as mandated by the Department of Education.	3.43	VMI
3. The school has a bulletin board where the profile of the school including DRRM information are posted.	3.17	MI
4. An updated evacuation plan is provided and posted at the school to provide guidance in setting the schools evacuation procedure.	3.15	MI
5. Yearly training needs analysis is conducted to be able to design appropriate training program for the SDRRM Team.	2.99	MI
Average Mean	3.23	MI

LEGEND: 3.26-4.00 *Very Much Implemented (VMI)*
 2.51-3.25 *Much Implemented (MI)*
 1.76-2.50 *Implemented (I)*
 1.00-1.75 *Not Implemented (NI)*

Table 9 shows the extent of implementation of stakeholders on disaster preparedness in connection to school disaster management. It has an average mean of 3.23 with a descriptive equivalent of much implemented indicating a slightly not implemented programs regarding school disaster management. The area obtaining the highest mean of 3.43 with descriptive equivalent of very much implemented is SDDRM Team conducts yearly activities such as fire and earthquake drills as mandated by the department of education. Having a mean of 2.99, the lowest mean obtained, interpreted

as much implemented is yearly training needs analysis is conducted to be able to design appropriate training program for the SDRRM Team.

The result corroborates with the study of Regis (2020), that the implementation of schools in there is study is highly implemented when it comes disaster preparedness with regards to school disaster management.

Table 10 Extent of implementation of disaster preparedness regarding risk reduction and resilience education

RISK REDUCTION AND RESELIENCE EDUCATION	M	DE
1. Disaster Risk Reduction and Management activities are included in co-curricular activities such as family day, IP Month and Linggo ng Wika.	3.29	MI
2. The school through DepEd Order No. 5 s. 2014, participates in Gulayan sa Paaralan, ecological waste management and tree growing and caring.	2.60	MI
3. Disaster Risk Reduction posters are seen at the school vicinity.	3.35	VMI
4. There are active community organizations that promote and support schools' endeavors on DRRM like local non- government organizations, religious institutions, community education and others.	1.89	I
5. Stakeholders are involved in planning of the activities for the school by the SDRRM Team.	3.21	MI
Average Mean	2.87	MI

LEGEND: 3.26-4.00 *Very Much Implemented (VMI)*
 2.51-3.25 *Much Implemented (MI)*
 1.76-2.50 *Implemented (I)*
 1.00-1.75 *Not Implemented (NI)*

Table 10 shows the extent of implementation of stakeholders on disaster preparedness program with regards to risk reduction and resilience education. The average mean obtained was 2.87 interpreted as moderately implemented. It implies that there are some of the programs that were less implemented. The result is associated with the disaster risk reduction posters are seen at the school vicinity having a mean of 3.35 interpreted as very much implemented. On the other hand, active community organizations that promote and support school's endeavors on DRRM like non-

government organizations, religious institutions, community education and others got the lowest mean of 1.89 interpreted as implemented.

The result of the study agrees to the study conducted by Syahputri et al. (2022) that integration of risk reduction and resilience education in the curriculum is not highly implemented as to the perception of the respondents.

Table 11 Extent of implementation of disaster preparedness regarding communication and information sources

COMMUNICATION AND INFORMATION SOURCES	M	DE
1. There are available communication channel that stakeholders can access/ receive information regarding Disaster Risk Reduction and Management.	3.33	VMI
2. There are available information sources that stakeholders can access/ receive information regarding Disaster Risk Reduction and Management.	3.41	VMI
3. Posters of updated emergency numbers are posted in important places in the school like the classroom and offices.	3.21	MI
4. Stakeholders are active in participating in the Information Education Campaign of the SDDRM Team.	3.26	VMI
5. The school conducts meetings with stakeholders regarding disaster preparedness activities of school.	3.26	VMI
6. The school organizes the SPG (Supreme Student Government) that helps in the information dissemination and communication of disaster preparedness program of the school.	3.41	VMI
Average Mean	3.31	VMI

LEGEND: 3.26-4.00 *Very Much Implemented (VMI)*
 2.51-3.25 *Much Implemented (MI)*
 1.76-2.50 *Implemented (I)*
 1.00-1.75 *Not Implemented (NI)*

As gleaned in Table 11, stakeholders' implementation of disaster preparedness with regards to communication and information sources is much implemented as represented by the average mean of 3.31. It implies that stakeholders implement disaster preparedness programs at school. It is associated with the availability of information sources that stakeholders can access/ receive information regarding Disaster Risk Reduction and Management with a mean of 3.41 interpreted as very much implemented, obtaining the highest mean. While the lowest mean obtained is 3.21 with descriptive equivalent of much implemented which is posters of updated emergency numbers are

posted in important places in the school like the classroom and offices. This implies that stakeholders though implemented some of the programs not all were fully implemented.

Table 12 Extent of implementation of disaster preparedness

LEVEL OF DISASTER AWARENESS OF STAKEHOLDERS	M	DE
Safe Learning Environment	2.72	MI
School Disaster Management	3.23	MI
Risk Reduction and Resilience Education	2.87	MI
Communication and Information Sources	3.31	VMI
Total Average Mean	3.03	MI

Table 11 shows the extent of implementation of stakeholders on disaster preparedness program implanted at school. The total average mean is 3.03 interpreted as much implemented showing that stakeholders have a lower participation in the activities regarding implementation of disaster preparedness program of their respective schools.

The result of the study does not corroborate to the study of Tizon and Comighud (2020) where the extent of implementation in their respondent is very much implemented. The result differs such that the respondents were the school heads of the schools where they conducted that research. Moreover, they used the weighted mean as basis for the result while in this study only the mean was given because each area of the indicators in the questionnaire were not given weight.

Difference on the Extent of Implementation on disaster preparedness of public elementary schools when grouped according to the profile of the respondents.

As shown in table 5, SDRRM Coordinators obtained the highest perception in terms of extent of implementation on disaster preparedness at school as shown in the mean of 3.26, followed by the teachers with the mean of 3.23. Next are the PTA Presidents with an average mean of 3.11 followed by the school heads with an average mean of 2.97. The lowest in mean is 2.95 which is obtained by the PTA Presidents. Nevertheless, the five group’s meaning, though interpreted as much implemented, it reveals slight numerical differences. The difference lies in the safe learning environment which obtained the highest rating among the five respondents. Teachers gave a rating of 3.41, school heads a rating of 3.43, SDRRM Coordinators with 3.61 PTA presidents with a rating of 3.48 and grade six pupils with a rating of 3.25.

Statistical analysis shows that the p-value of 0.69 is higher than the alpha value of 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it accepts the hypothesis that there is no significant

difference in the extent of implementation of public elementary schools in disaster preparedness when school profile is considered.

The finding implies that regardless of the school profiles of respondents, stakeholders have similar perceptions, indicating that their school profile is not a factor in the implementation of disaster preparedness programs.

Table 13 Difference on the Level of Awareness on disaster preparedness of public elementary schools when grouped according to the profile of the respondents.

Indicator	PTA Presi- dent	Tea- chers	Grade Six Pupils	SDRRM Coor- dinators	School Heads
A. Safe Learning Environment	2.80 MI	2.78 MI	2.71 MI	2.79 MI	2.18 MI
B. School Disaster Management	3.03 MI	3.6 MI	3.12 MI	3.47 VMI	3.06 MI
C. Risk Reduction and Resilience Education	3.14 MI	3.13 MI	3.73 VMI	3.17 MI	3.22 MI
D. Communication and Information Sources	3.48 VMI	3.41 VMI	3.25 MI	3.61 VMI	3.43 VMI
Average	3.11 MI	3.23 MI	2.96 MI	3.26 MI	2.97 MI

p-value= 0.69

$\alpha= 0.05$

not significant

The findings of this study corroborate to the study of Morcilla (2023) where the result show that there isn't outstanding variety in that frame of mind of preparation and level of inner partners' execution in risk counteraction and the executives for school fiascos programs with an importance limit of 0.05. The way that having no perceptible change shows that the responses inward partners don't vary so much.

In the implementation of the disaster preparedness program there are some that stakeholders did not fully implement and that should be given more attention to as evident in the much implemented descriptive equivalent of the general average mean of extent of implementation of disaster preparedness program at school. One way to bridge the gap is the crafting of an action plan that schools may implement. According to Hanna (2022),

action plans are essential in fulfilling your goals and objectives. It is a guide on how to step by step fulfill what you want to achieve.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Stakeholders are well-versed in the programs offered at each school, but their participation in the execution process is comparatively low.
2. Many of the ongoing programs have either not gotten enough attention or have been carried out insufficiently.
3. An action plan is needed to fulfill the goal of the disaster preparedness program that have been carried out insufficiently.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were drawn:

1. The school may pursue the continuation of the information and education campaign of the DRRM through the of conduct meetings with stakeholders regarding disaster preparedness activities of the school for it is essential in encouraging cooperation, coordination, and communication in disaster preparedness initiatives.
2. The school may coordinate with an active community organization that promote and support schools' endeavors on DRRM like local non- government organizations, religious institutions, community education and others through crafting requests letters and memorandum of agreements that would bind the school and active community organization partnership.
3. Utilization of the proposed action plan based on the finished the finished research.
4. Other research with the same study may be used to support the result of this study.
5. Further study is recommended to include parameters like the barriers in the implementation of disaster preparedness program.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before conducting the proposed study, the researcher undertook the following procedures to ensure ethical considerations in the conduct of a research. The researcher first secured written permission to float the researcher instruments from the school authorities of the intended informants of the study; A letter accompanied the survey/research instrument that was given to the target respondents/informants/subjects indicating among others; to wit: 1) the participants identity would not be divulged in the current study in compliance to the provisions of the Data Privacy Law; 2) all information and data from the participants/respondents/subjects of the current study would be held in strict confidentiality; 3) when the respondents/subjects answered the survey questionnaire/instrument, that means they agree to participate in the study as respondents; 4) the responses in the questionnaire/instrument is presented in aggregate

and not as individual perceptions; and 5) the research conducted is primarily for academic requirement only.

The researcher declares that all materials/findings borrowed from other sources and included in his/her thesis/dissertation are properly cited and acknowledged.

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